

influenced yield. USG at 75 kg N/ha gave the maximum yield (6.15 t/ha) (see table). During rabi, application method and the interaction of N level and source were significant. At 100 kg N/ha, USG gave the maximum yield (4.05 t/ha), equal to yields with coal tar- and neem cake-coated urea and with USG applied at 75 kg N/ha. Split application of N was best.

In kharif, USG, urea coated with neem cake (20%), and coal tar (1%) at higher N levels produced significantly higher yields than PU. In rabi, USG placement at lower N levels produced yields equal to those with neem cake, coal tar, and USG applied at higher N levels, resulting in 25% N savings. $\mathcal{L}$

Influence of different N sources and levels on rice grain yield, Tamil Nadu, India.

N level (kg/ha) and sources	Yield (t/ha)		
	100% basal	50% basal + 50% split	Mean
<i>TKM9 in kharif</i>			
<i>50 kg N/ha</i>			
PU	5.4	5.5	4.50
Neem cake-blended (20%)	5.5	5.5	5.50
Coal tar-coated (1%)	5.4	5.5	5.45
USG	5.7	5.8	5.75
<i>75 kg N/ha</i>			
PU	5.6	5.8	5.70
Neem cake-blended (20%)	6.0	6.2	6.10
Coal tar-coated (1%)	5.9	6.2	6.05
USG	6.2	6.1	6.15
Mean	5.7	5.8	
<i>IR20 in rabi</i>			
<i>75 kg N/ha</i>			
PU	3.5	3.6	3.55
Neem cake-blended (20%)	3.7	3.7	3.70
Coal tar-coated (1%)	3.5	3.7	3.60
USG	4.0	3.9	3.95
<i>100 kg N/ha</i>			
PU	3.6	4.0	3.80
Neem cake-blended (20%)	3.8	4.0	3.90
Coal tar-coated (1%)	4.0	4.1	4.05
USG	4.0	4.1	4.05
Mean	3.76	3.88	

CD at 5%

N X source
Application method
N X sources X application method

1984 rabi

0.22
0.09
ns

1985 kharif

0.29
ns
ns

Integrated organic and inorganic nitrogen fertilizer in lowland rice

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The effectiveness of urea or urea supergranules (USG) applied alone or in combination with azolla or rice straw was evaluated during 1984 kharif. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Soil was clay loam with a pH of 8.2, 1.10% organic matter, 201 kg available N/ha, 5 kg available P/ha, and 427 kg available K/ha.

Urea and USG were compared at 58 and 87 kg N/ha. Azolla and straw were used to substitute for 29 kg N/ha. P and K were applied basally at 22 kg P/ha and 42 kg K/ha.

Fresh azolla was incorporated 1 d before transplanting. To ensure proper decomposition, straw was chopped and incorporated 15 d before transplanting. Urea was applied 1/3 basal, 1/3 at tillering, and 1/3 at flowering. USG was deep placed 1 wk after transplanting. N level significantly influenced yield (see table). Deep placement of USG was significantly superior to urea at all N levels. Yield was highest with deep placement of USG at 87 kg N/ha. The relatively lower yield with broadcast application of urea was presumably due to losses of N through ammonia volatilization and denitrification. Incorporating azolla with USG was as good as USG alone. Incorporating straw with USG was as

Effect of source and level of N on yield and return on investment. Coimbatore, India.

Source	N (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Return on investment (%)
Control	0	2.8	51
PU	58	3.5	80
USG	58	4.2	106
PU + azolla	29	3.3	66
PU + straw	29	3.3	46
USG + azolla	29	3.5	72
USG + straw	29	3.4	50
PU	87	4.3	113
USG	87	5.2	147
PU + azolla	29	4.2	104
PU + straw	29	4.1	76
USG + azolla	29	5.0	138
USG + straw	29	4.9	108
SED.		155.8	
CD (P = 0.05)		315.9	

effective as USG alone. The N and P fertilizers might have enhanced response to straw incorporation.

Azolla or straw combined with urea did not increase yield.

The net income and return on investment were highest with deep placement of USG at 87 kg N/ha. Deep placed USG was more profitable than split applied urea at all levels of N. Incorporation of azolla or straw with either urea or USG resulted in lower net income and return on investment than complete application of urea or USG. Azolla and straw involved high cultivation costs. $\mathcal{L}$

Evaluating rate, timing, and method of N application using tracer technique

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To study rate, timing, and method of N application, ammonium sulfate enriched

at 5% atom excess level with N-15 was used as a tracer. The field trial was conducted on clay alluvial soil with pH 8.4, 1.77% organic matter, 1,940 ppm total N, 37.2 ppm inorganic N, 16.8 ppm Olsen's P, 580 ppm ammonium acetate extracted K, EC 1.21 dS/m, and 53% CaCO₃. The experiment was a complete randomized design with four replications. All plots received a blanket application of P and K.